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Machines in the Creative Process: Limitations Through Choreography

Colloquial Paper

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Machines in the Creative Process: Limitations Through Choreography

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Abstract

This practice-based project is a critique on our relationship with machines to foreground the necessity of continued human involvement. My approach is from the perspective of a classically trained ex-dancer in a design research context. Using choreography as a medium, I propose that affecting elements of the creative process with algorithms may illustrate a limitation to automated integration within society. I create accessories for dancers as expert users as one component of a human-machine-human communication system. My research focusses on dancers' visceral responses to the vibrating stimuli delivered by the wearable devices. Although I also use motion capture technology to collect source material, I exclude the use of avatars for interpretation by end-users. The live performance itself is used as illustration intended for insight into potential future societal machine integration.

Keywords: communication system, wearable, choreography, algorithm, machine

Purpose of the research and its importance to the field

In its rawest form an algorithm is like a recipe. I refer to them as *intangible* machines instead of digital as they do not necessarily have to be computer generated. They are a series of instructions designed to execute a function. In theory, an algorithm does not cost money, need sustenance or get sick. But building them does, for the simple reason that humans are required to enable these processes. How long this remains equally symbiotic is currently anyone's prediction.

On the topic of Silicon Valley supercomputers amassing consumer data without financial benefit to their users, computer philosopher Jaron Lanier outlines during a televised interview, "...you might get free music but the possibility of you ever becoming a self-sustaining musician becomes more and more reduced. You might get free lessons but the possibility of you ever becoming a teacher becomes more and more reduced. Eventually this will apply to every profession because everything will become more and more software mediated as we get better at technology in this century." (Lanier, 2013). He suggests that the human-machine symbiosis has a shelf life. But perhaps shifting the weight between the components themselves may shed light on this doomed path to destruction?

It is this interrelation that I am suggesting requires deeper questioning in order to foreground the necessity of continued human involvement. And while this is already being asked by the science and technology sectors, I propose that artistic interventions may provide new information, equalise our discomfort with machine integration and spark further key questions. Situated within dance choreography as a medium, this project aims to address our pandemic fear of machines.

Brief survey of background and related work

The digital and choreographic spheres have been in conversation for several decades. In *Choreography and Computers*, A. Michael Noll outlines the, "... possibilities for the application of computer technology to problems in choreography and dance notation." (Noll, 1967, pp. 1) He mentions his preference for, "...some drastic changes in the present choreographic process which in the long run might be a better solution to many problems including ballet preservation and dance notation." He suggests that the computer ballet system he has devised would enable, "...certain portions of creative the process [to be] filled in by the computer which might be programmed to learn the choreographer's style. (Noll, 1967, pp. 2)"

He unknowingly described the tool Wayne McGregor designed to digitally affect choreography in collaboration with Google Arts & Culture. Entitled *Living Archive*, McGregor has, "...called it a performance experiment," (Easter 2019). For the world premiere at the Music Center's Dorothy Chandler Pavilion in Los Angeles, McGregor used their algorithm to choreograph *The Dante Project* (*Inferno*). Google developed an algorithm that predicts the next series of movements in each dancer's specific style by absorbing Studio Wayne McGregor's 25-year archive of choreography in the style of the ten dancers. It recreates their movements, tempo and dynamic in stick figures on a large screen for he and his dancers to engage with directly. "Presented with options for possible sequences of movement, the dancer could then either use the phrase, interpret it in their own way or use it to inspire improvisation. [...] It's a real recursive process between the dancer and the AI system," the choreographer said. He explained the process: "It's exploiting opportunities in the data you can never see yourself," (Easter 2019). Google Team Lead Damien Henry adds, "This produces a total of 30 potential choreography sequences, which at the moment last about ten seconds, and which are displayed on a computer screen using a similar 'skeleton' visual. McGregor chooses which one he would like to use. Then, whatever the dancer does can be recorded again and re-injected in the machine..." (LePrince-Ringuet, 2018). Henry says that the Google tool is not meant to invent moves that have never been seen before. "The point is not to replace the choreographer [...] but to create options in a very efficient and fast way, so that the creative process never stops. The creativity will come from the use that Wayne will make of these options," (LePrince-Ringuet, 2018). McGregor clarifies: "The choices are still mine. I'm the source, I'm the person at the beginning' [...] I see this more as an opportunity – I love being in the game," (LePrince-Ringuet, 2018).

Noll suggests another way of overcoming the documentation issue would be using video footage as the source material. He explains, "Different camera positions could be used simultaneously so that the three-dimensional location of the dancers could be calculated by the computer. The films would be analyzed by the computer and converted into motion patterns," (Noll, 1967, pp. 2). While the technological capabilities of computers was obviously less developed in the 1960's his proposition is essentially what William Forsythe, Norah Zuniga Shaw and Maria Palazzi created in 2007 with *Synchronous Objects*. Forsythe's piece *One Flat Thing*, reproduced (OFTr) was the basis for the notation tool developed at the Advanced Computing Center for the Arts and Design and Department of Dance at Ohio State University. It was demonstrated at the 2009 Siggraph Information Aesthetic Showcase, "...to enrich cross-disciplinary investigation and creativity by revealing deep structures of choreographic thinking through a vivid collection of information objects in the form of 3D computer animation, annotation, and interactive graphics," (Palazzi, 2009). It was the prototype for the *Motion Bank* project that followed which is the choreographic tool available for public use (deLahunta, 2013). It contains several examples of 'dance scores' which have been created with this interactive application. Seeing a complex piece of award-winning choreography dissected into animated cues attached to each dancer is innovative and aesthetically interesting. This visual analysis does offer material production possibilities (dance scores) through a choreographer's interpretation of the tool, however it was originally composed for notation and documentation.

In their *chor-rnn* choreographic system Louise and Luka Crnkovic-Friis have built an algorithm that uses machine learning to acquire understanding how a given performer dances (Crnkovic-Friis and Crnkovic-Friis, 2016). The algorithm is intended to act as a choreographic tool to predict what the next movements might be in that particular style. Also using MoCap technology to capture the dancer's movement they tested their 'stick figure' avatar after approximately ten minutes, six hours and forty-eight hours of learning. Only after the latter did it begin to understand the joint relations, syntax and style well. When speaking of future projects they go on to say, "For comparison state of the art speech recognition models use 100+ hours of data (and it is considered to be a major bottleneck in that field of research) [...]. It is currently limited to

producing choreography for one dancer and cannot not yet generate the semantics in choreography,” (Crnkovic-Friis and Crnkovic-Friis, 2016, pp. 123).

At the Second International Conference on Computational Creativity Mexico in 2011, Kristin Carlson, Thecla Schiphorst and Philippe Pasquier presented their version of a computer assisted choreographic system, Scuddle: Generating Movement Catalysts for Computer-Aided Choreography (Carlson et al, 2011). For their purposes they break dance creation into three stages: movement, sequence, choreography. Likely due to Schiphorst’s involvement (Schiphorst, 1986, pp. iii) with the development of DanceForms (previously called LifeForms) they build on this system as it, “...focuses on all three stages of the choreographic process, allowing complex movement to be designed and viewed with a high level of detail,” (Carlson et al, 2011, pp. 124). They contrast DanceForms and Scuddle with other existing systems in a chart (pp. 124) that includes Tour Jete, Pirouette (Yu and Johnson, 2003); Web 3D Composer (Soga et al, 2006); Genome (Lapointe and Époque, 2005); Dancing (Eckert, 2015); and Evolution (Dubbin, 2009) plus “Pre-1990 Systems”. They break down each systems into which stage of the choreographic process they affect, the source material, the data-altering mechanism, the final selection method, how the choreographic data is shown and the level of level of movement fidelity.

Despite the various developments in computer-aided choreographic systems and processes, Noll anticipation of them to be a, “...completely new creative process, [that] might result in new dance forms” (Noll, 1967, pp. 2) unifies their differing intended applications through a common aspiration. His conclusion about the state of human movement notation and choreography, “...recommend[s] an investigation of the possibilities of the computer,” (Noll, 1967, pp. 3) and this has clearly been taken seriously.

Description of the proposed approach

While I often employ music and sound to inspire my choreography and ultimately accompany a performance of work, I am intentionally excluding it from this study. There are already several components to consider:

- my choreographic outputs as source material;
- the MoCap system;
- the algorithm that processes the data generated by MoCap technology;
- the different wearables I build including the shape, size, intended placement (Figure 1.);
- the materials from which they are constructed (knit, moulded leather, latex, strapping, elastic, etc.);
- the type of physical stimulus embedded in the wearable (Figure 2.);
- the location of the wearable on the user’s body (Figure 3);
- and the physicality, training and interpretation of the expert user (dancer) themselves.

Figure 1. (2018) Moulded leather accessory with elastic straps and plastic buckles

Figure 2. (2018) Pager motor suspended in silicone with e-textile as conductor; moulded leather casing on front abdomen

Figure 3. (2019) synthetic knit panel with leather casing attached with elastic

All of which present their own variables that may have an effect on each trial's results. Adding sound or music to this communication process would add an entirely new level of complexity when capturing the responses of the end-user. However, using a score may be helpful when demonstrating how the system works to an audience. For the time being I am leaving the question as to whether the viewer will be aware of the physical stimulus contained in the wearable or not open.

Due to my own conservatory-style training in ballet, Graham, Limón, contemporary and jazz techniques I have narrowed my user recruitment to adult professional dancers with similar histories. I am targeting dance artists who also have dance education at university level. This tends to ensure a common verbal and physical vocabulary, which is useful in effectively capturing the users' responses during observation and interviews. This background also encourages use of the whole body in physical expression. It also means capturing details of extension, articulation and dynamic are essential in understanding the dancers' visceral responses. Heterophenomenological approaches are proving effective for deeper response comprehension (Kozel, 2008).

The motion capture system I am currently using is OptiTrack software with a Rokoko suit. However I have already identified limitations relative to contemporary dance improvisation. The avatars created by the nodes on the Rokoko suit divide the

spine in 2 sections plus the pelvis. The suit also does not go beyond the knuckles and the head is represented by a vertical bar. These do not offer sufficient fidelity for this type of dance work. There are other options available, like the Perception Neuron suit employed by choreographer Alexander Whitey in some recently published digital experiments (Whitley, 2020). A Captury Live system developed by Dr. Nils Hasler, Michal Richter, Svilen Dimitrov and Christian Theobalt may also be a possibility as it is marker-less, only uses cameras (Gibson and Martelli, 2018).

The aim here is to minimise the variables within each experiment for digestible analysis of the results. The algorithm is a variation of a prototype I co-designed with biostatistician Leah Gerber Davis at Duke University in 2016. However that example was designed to support the creation of garment silhouettes through polygon generation. This is an adaptation that also uses an algorithm as part of the creative process, however the intent, input and output data formats have been changed. Here, MoCap data in Python is being translated into morse code-like sequences of stimulus materialised through a battery-powered pager motor embedded in a wearable.

I am interested in dancers' interpretations to the stimuli and how my choreography would be expressed once processed by the algorithm. What movement languages might be created? What materials are best to build the wearable devices? How do the users feel about automation in society after being in this choreographic process? Would audiences change their perception of machine integration after experiencing a demonstration of the system?

Expected contribution

The existing choreographic systems and digital dance work have an aspect of animation or use computer to visualise the human dancers interactions. The human-machine interrelation they utilise are also concerned with ending up a visual in which the choreographer can transpose to their dancer(s). I do not yet see an example of a choreographic system that contains the physical instigation element. These systems appear to use traditional dance interpretation methods to retransmit the digital/virtual world back into the actual one: the dancers either watch the avatars and interpret the movement sequences in their own bodies. Or the choreographer analyses the movements or phrases presented to them by the digital avatars and makes creative choices with which to direct their dancers. In my project the visual aspect of my system comes through the dancer's visceral response to the wearable giving them a physical point of initiation or instruction. It may be the system's design itself that is yet unprecedented, perhaps because I am not using animation, avatars or other visual cues as components. I make the wearables myself, provide the choreographic source material, co-create the algorithm affecting the stimulus, and interpret the results manifested in the end-user. It is this specific positioning that I have not yet seen. The co-created algorithm specific to movement impetus may also be the contribution.

Progress towards goals

Over the progress of this project it has become logical to break it down into separate components. Although the system is intended as a chain reaction communication system, it has not been necessary to build each component in their intended reactionary order.

Key next steps are testing the wearables on actual expert user (dancers) *without* the algorithm, record the responses and analysing the results to inform the next round of prototypes. The movement data capture methods (MoCap) need further exploring, likely via other resources due to the restrictions of OptiTrack and Rokoko. The algorithm is still in development with the biostatistician now that we have narrowed the language down to Python. I anticipate a subsequent study will be instigating the stimuli by the algorithm's patterns instead of manual inputs.

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